

Experimental investigation on behaviour of composite deck slab using M25 grade concrete for different profiled sheets

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ABSTRACT:

The composite deck slabs have recently been used in a variety of structures, including office buildings, industrial warehouses, hospitals, schools, parking lots, and residential buildings, due to their several advantages such as faster construction, increased strength, and lower weight when compared to conventional reinforced concrete slabs. The deck slabs are especially useful in multi-story and inner-city buildings where space is restricted. The composite deck slab comprises of a profiled deck sheet, reinforcement mesh, and concrete. The profiled sheet functions as both a permanent formwork and shear reinforcement for a cast-in-place concrete topping. The steel serves as the concrete's permanent tension reinforcement and provides mechanical interlocking with concrete, allowing the two materials to function as single structural unit. Several studies have been conducted to investigate the flexural behaviour of composite deck slabs in order to determine the responses viz. load carrying capacity, deflection, strain energy, ductility ratio, and modes of failure considering different types of profiled sheets and concretes. In this study, a rigorous review of the literature is carried out to understand the flexural behaviour of composite deck slabs with various types of profiled sheets under two-line loading. The study reveals that, use of profiled sheets with embossments and shear connectors in the composite deck slab contributes in enhancing its load carrying capacity and stiffness with reduction in deflection values. The authors recommends the need of exploring the flexural behaviour of composite deck slabs using different shapes of profiled sheets without and with embossments and shear connectors.

Key words: Composite deck slab, profiled sheets, two-line loading, flexural behaviour.

1. Introduction

1.1 General

This dissertation work mainly focuses on study of flexural behaviour of composite deck slab using normal strength concrete of M25 grade and considering different shapes of profiled sheets (viz. trapezoidal, corrugated and rectangular sheet) for determining the structural responses viz. load carrying capacity and deflection under two-line loading.

1.2 Definition of composite deck slab

Composite deck slabs, that are mainly made of structural concrete and cold-formed profiled steel decking, are increasing in popularity in buildings with steel frames worldwide in recent years. Concrete is poured during construction to make a continuous one-way composite slab, and the steel decking is usually continuous over two spans between the supporting steel beams (Islam et al., 2020; Chen S.,2003). When compared to standard concrete slabs, composite slabs offer various advantages, including speed, safety, efficiency, and an enhanced strength-to-weight ratio, and they are commonly used in the construction business (Islam et al.,2020).

The profiled steel decking in the composite deck slab flooring system has two primary functions. First, it serves as a permanent formwork to hold the wet concrete placed during construction. Second, it acts as an external reinforcement for the slab, carrying the load generated by the positive bending moment throughout its life. If the strength given by the steel

decking is insufficient, extra reinforcing may be placed in the concrete slab. Further nominal light mesh reinforcement bars are necessary to account for shrinkage and temperature, generally in the form of welded wire cloth (Chen S.,2003).

1.3 Components of composite deck slab

A composite deck slab consists of various components and the details of these components is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.No.1.1 Components of a composite deck slab (Gholamhoseini, A.,2018).

A typical composite deck slab consists of the following components:

1) Profiled deck sheet

Profile deck sheet is the vital component of composite deck slab. The common shapes available in the market for profile deck sheet are Rectangular, Trapezoidal and Corrugated with varying heights and corrugation depths. Profile deck sheet works as a framework under constructional loads and in composite action it behaves as tensile reinforcement also it supports compressive resistance with concrete (Choradiya P.,2016)

2) Reinforcement

Steel reinforcement is a key component of the slab design, as the deck profile resists tensile pressures in the slab's bottom, but the composite floor cannot function properly without a form of reinforcement in the concrete. The reinforcement in the slab reduces cracking of concrete, improves load distribution and also improves the fire resistance of the finished composite floor (SMD Ltd.,2025).

3) Concrete:

The concrete is placed directly onto the composite floor deck profile, forming the mixed section of the slab and providing the required strength and rigidity for bearing the design loads (European Committee for Standardization 2004).

4) Shear connector:

The chemical or mechanical (Shear Connectors) interlocking plays an important role in composite action of both profile deck sheet and concrete. This helps in enhancing ultimate load carrying capacity of concrete deck slab (Choradiya P.,2016).

2. Motivation of present work

The emerging new fields in the civil engineering and the development demand taking in consideration there is need to improve the performance of the building. This can be done with introducing new construction techniques in the recent era one of which is the composite structures. The most efficient use of the two material properties to construct faster better and efficient building construction. This lead has created an interest to study the behaviour of the composite elements. For any new thing the behaviour of each element is necessary which will help us to forecast the behaviour of the whole structure as a whole. The analysis of the composite deck slab by considering the provision of single type of profiled sheet is completed but the comparative flexural behaviour of composite deck slabs provided with different types of profiled sheets is yet to be done. Hence, the analysis of flexural behaviour of composite deck slab cast with M25 grade concrete and considering different profiled sheets (viz. Trapezoidal, corrugated and rectangular), using appropriate (Abaqus) software for determining the load carrying capacity and deflection under two-line loading and validation of analysis results with the results of experimentation is done in the current thesis.

3. Literature Review

The following section contains a review of research articles published by numerous researchers in various journals:

Gupta et al. (2012) experimentally examined the concrete composite deck slab's shear bond strength using bending tests with different shear spans (300–675 mm) (Eurocode 4). M-K and partial shear connection (PSC) methods are used to calculate the longitudinal shear bond strength between concrete and steel decks. According to the study's findings, the m-k method results are weaker than the experimental method by 43%. The authors conclude that PSC approach provides the optimal design to determine the ductile behaviour of concrete composite deck slabs, and novel profiles must be validated.

Kaveh and Ahangaran. (2012) optimized composite floor systems using a Social Harmony Search (SHS) algorithm, considering slab, beam, and stud parameters under AISC-LRFD constraints. The results indicated that SHS achieved the highest cost savings of 16.62% for shored floors and 3.22% for unshored floors, outperforming Harmony Search (HS), Improved Harmony Search (HIS), Highly Reliable Harmony Search (HRHS), and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) methods. Authors conclude that the SHS model showed faster convergence (30–40% quicker) and provided the most economical designs, proving highly effective for cost-efficient composite floor optimization.

Kaveh and Massoudi (2012) applied an Ant Colony System (ACS) to optimize the cost of composite floor systems by selecting slab, beam, and shear connector variables under AISC-LRFD constraints. The results indicated that ACS model achieved significant cost reductions of about 10–20% depending on span and load conditions, and consistently delivered economical designs with correct strength and serviceability performance. Authors conclude that the method proved efficient, providing substantial cost savings and a practical optimization tool for composite floor systems.

Mahfuz et al. (2016) investigated the structural performance of composite deck slabs made of various concrete kinds, such as engineered cementitious composite (ECC), lightweight self-consolidating concrete (LWSCC), ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC), and self-compacting concrete (SSC). To evaluate strength, ductility, and energy absorption, slabs were put through fatigue cycles, post-fire conditions, and static loading tests. The results indicated that ECC and UHPC slabs showed the highest strength, with 20–50% greater load capacity than SCC and HSC. Fatigue reduced strength only by 5–12%, while reinforcement improved capacity by 10–20%. ECC had the best energy absorption (+40–60%) and retained about 80% of its strength after fire, compared to 20–35% loss in others. Post-fire stiffness dropped by 25–45%, least in ECC (20%). The authors concludes that composite slab applications that are subjected to strain and fire require the selection of a suitable type of concrete.

Ashraf et al. (2017) experimentally conducted testing on a new type of composite slab produced from lightweight aggregate concrete and closed profiled steel sheeting (LCCS) to evaluate longitudinal shear-bond behaviour, failure modes, and the accuracy of existing design methods. Initial cracking occurred at 16–30% of ultimate load, while initial slip occurred at 50–86% of ultimate load. Increasing steel-sheet thickness from 0.8 mm to 1.0 mm increased ultimate capacity by 23%, with little gain from 1.0 to 1.2 mm. Slabs with studs showed 26–50% higher ultimate load, 21% more deflection, and up to 89% reduction in slip compared to slabs without studs. Long-span slabs developed a new mixed-mode failure, showing bending capacity with significant slip. The authors conclude that Slabs with studs substantially enhance capacity and slip control, and traditional design methods remain accurate for this new slab type.

Sultana et al. (2018) experimentally evaluated the performance of composite deck slabs provided with trapezoidal profiled sheets of varying dimensions and also by using shear connectors. The results of study indicate that use of shear connectors contributed in improving the bonding strength of all the slabs. Additionally, the trapezoidal profiled sheets with larger dimension for top width, bottom width demonstrated the highest load capacity, showing a 27.7% increase over Slab 1 and 12.2% over Slab 2, while Slab 2 carried 13.8% more load than Slab 1. In contrast, Slab 1 exhibited the least deflection, performing 71.4% better in stiffness than both Slab 2 and Slab 3, indicating that increased strength in Slabs 2 and 3 was accompanied by higher deflection. The author concludes that Provision of shear connectors increases the bonding strength in the slabs.

Islam et al. (2020) experimentally investigated and compared three types of profiled steel sheet–concrete composite slabs (PSSCCS): Type-I (with studs), Type-II (with minimum reinforcement), and Type-III (without reinforcement). The ultimate capacity, failure modes, and stress-strain behaviour of PSSCCS are observed. The results indicated that Type-II slabs carry 116% more load, and Type-I slabs carry 200% more load than the non-reinforced Type-III slab. Type-II showed

roughly 180–200% ductility, and Type-I reached 280–300% ductility compared with the baseline. Failure severity was highest in Type-III (100%), reduced to 50–60% in Type-II, and lowest (30–40%) in Type-I. The authors concludes that ultimate capacity of composite slab using reinforcement and studs is increased two times and three times than reference test of no reinforcement slab.

Raman et al. (2021) examined experimentally how different cold-formed profiled sheets affected the way bolted shear connectors connected the composite deck slab actions. The ductility ratio, strain energy, ultimate load carrying capacity versus deflection, load versus slip, and failure modes of composite slabs are all evaluated using profiled sheets of three different types: trapezoidal, rectangular, and dovetailed (or re-entrant). When compared to slabs with different profiled sheets, the results indicated that dovetailed composite deck slabs' load carrying capacities are 5.35% and 22.03% greater than rectangular and trapezoidal profiled composite slabs, respectively. trapezoidal profiled composite slabs attained the maximum strain energy of 2.98 kN/m. The ductility ratio for trapezoidal profile is 36.3% and 55% higher when compared to rectangular and dovetailed profiled composite slabs. Authors conclude that the composite deck slab with dovetailed profiled sheets performs better.

Rajkumar et al. (2021) experimentally studied the flexural behaviour of composite slab prepared using trapezoidal profiled sheet under four-point loading for determining load carrying capacity, and deformation. The results indicated that deflection remained low (up to 2.5 mm), followed by a sudden jump to 5.2 mm at failure. Flexural cracks formed directly under the line loads and progressed to the slab's top surface, with no additional cracks near mid-span at failure. The specimen also showed poor shear-bond performance, evidenced by early minor separation at 10 kN and significant end slip (3.6 mm) at failure. Ultimately, the deck sheet fully separated from the concrete, resulting in sudden collapse, and the slab achieved an ultimate load capacity of 32.8 kN. The authors concludes that the load carrying capacity of composite deck slab can be enhance by improving bond characteristics between steel decking and concrete.

Lim et al. (2021) experimentally performed testing on a conventional slab and two composite slabs (0.75 mm and 1.0 mm decks) under four-point bending to identify the parameters viz. load carrying capacity, ductility and deflection. The results indicated that load capacity increased by 537% with a 0.75 mm deck and by 823% with a 1.0 mm deck compared to the RC slab, while the thicker deck (1.0 mm) carried 45% more load than the 0.75 mm deck and adding the steel deck increased ductility by 100.9% compared to the conventional slab. In terms of deflection the composite slabs showed 20–75% lower deflection than RC slab. Authors conclude that composite metal decks greatly enhance flexural capacity, ductility, and serviceability, with thicker decks (1.0 mm) performing best.

Galatage et al. (2022) conducted a comparative experimental investigation using point loading to determine the load carrying capacity and deflection of reinforced concrete slabs and composite slabs with profiled steel sheets. According to the study's findings, when compared to the corresponding value of conventional slabs, the composite slab's load carrying capacity (flexural capacity) increases by 40.3% while its deflection decreases by 66%. The authors conclude that composite slabs are more serviceable than traditional slabs.

Garcia et al. (2023) have investigated the structural and serviceability performance of composite slabs cast with recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) for determining load carrying capacity, deflections by subjecting the composite deck slabs to four-point loading, 90 days sustained loading and loading respectively. The results of study indicate that load carrying capacity gets reduced marginally (7%) under four-point loading. However, under sustained loading for 90 days, the vertical deflection of slab increases by 5.35%. The authors conclude that the use of recycled aggregates needs to be done effectively to understand the structural and serviceability performance of composite deck slab.

Chandan et al. (2023) designed composite slabs using Ansys software, taking into account Fiber Reinforced Self-Compacting Concrete (FRSCC) and Plain Cement Concrete (PCC), and comparing the parameters—bending stress and deflection. According to the results, composite deck slabs made of regular PCC (plain cement concrete) have higher bending stress by 78.7%, and deflection by 161.5%, than composite deck slabs made of fibre-reinforced self-compacting concrete (FRSCC). The authors conclude that the necessary strength is attained by employing steel fibres as a reinforcing element.

Ashraf et al. (2023) experimentally examined the composite slabs' two-way load distribution, shear behaviour, and structural capability made of concrete and a newly shaped steel deck. To create the new contoured steel deck, 90° bends are made in the corrugated sheets to create hat sections, which are then positioned perpendicularly on a corrugated base sheet. Results indicated that slabs failed by flexural and shear-bond failure, with similar load capacity of 196 kN (with studs) and 189 kN (without studs). Both showed two-way action (64%–36% without studs; 79%–21% with studs). The deck's geometry provided strong longitudinal shear resistance, evidenced by 0 mm slip along the main direction due to the corrugated top-hats. The authors conclude that the newly created profiled steel deck can be employed in two-way composite slabs for shear and load capacity.

Yehia et al. (2023) experimentally examined how the reinforcement mesh ratio and shear connector spacing influenced the bond and structural behaviour of composite slabs. Abaqus is also used to examine the behaviour of composite slabs in order to assess their load carrying capacity, with the results validated through experimentation. The results indicated that Shear connectors increased ultimate load by 1% (500 mm) and 12% (250 mm). Steel mesh greatly improved strength, with $\phi 8$ mesh giving +18% and $\Phi 10$ mesh giving +145% higher ultimate load than plain slabs. Increasing span from 2.5 m to 3.5 m reduced capacity by 9–18% for connector slabs and 6–44% for mesh slabs. FE results matched experiments within 5–12% for load and 3–10% for deflection. The highest shear-bond strength occurred with $\Phi 10$ mesh (0.51 MPa). The authors conclude that increasing the shear gap of the connector and using a greater reinforcement mesh ratio improves the ultimate load carrying capability.

Zhao et al. (2025) examined the post-fire behaviour of closed profiled steel deck composite slab cast using recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) after exposing it to the ISO 834 fire curve for 90 minutes. After cooling, the slab was tested for residual loading to determine the failure pattern, load deflection response, and concrete stresses. The authors conclude that fire duration has a substantial influence on the slab's residual loading ratio, and that increasing the fire time (from 0 to 120 minutes) reduces the residual bearing capacity by an average of 32.5%.

Wang et al. (2025) experimental flexural tests were conducted on five slab specimens with varying hollow rates, reinforcement ratios, and steel sheet thicknesses. Finite element simulations and theoretical analyses were also performed to evaluate flexural bearing capacities under different anchorage conditions. Results indicated that inadequate anchorage led to end debonding and a significant reduction in flexural capacity. Increasing the reinforcement ratio from 0% to 0.6% improved the ultimate bearing capacity by 182.5% and the ductility coefficient by 246%, with ultimate deflection increasing 22.4 times. When the hollow rate was below 20%, its influence on bearing capacity, ductility, and crack width was minimal. Increasing steel sheet thickness reduced deformation and improved ductility, although with diminishing gains in strength. Theoretical predictions showed close agreement with experimental results, confirming the reliability of the proposed calculation method. The study offers practical guidance for the design of lightweight and high-performance composite floor systems.

Huong et al. (2025) experimentally investigated twelve steel–concrete composite slabs to evaluate the effects of Fiber content, Fiber type, layer arrangement and screw connector density on structural performance under monotonic loading. The study found that increasing Fiber content from 0.1% to 0.5% enhanced load capacity by 155%, demonstrating the strong contribution of Fiber bridging. Using hybrid steel–polypropylene Fibers improved strength by 64% compared to conventional RC slabs, while steel Fibers alone increased load resistance by approximately 45–50%. Placing FRC at the bottom layer increased capacity by 8–15% relative to reversed layering. Shear connectors had a major influence, with 200 mm screw spacing improving flexural strength by 2.6 times ($\approx 160\%$) over slabs without screws; reducing screw spacing from 300 mm to 200 mm increased load capacity by 20–51%. The authors conclude that using shear connectors significantly improves load capacity, ductility, and overall structural performance.

4. Aims and Objectives of Present Work

Following are the aims and objectives of the dissertation work: -

- 1) To design the concrete mix of M25 grade using the guidelines of IS Code.
- 2) To analyse the flexural behaviour of composite deck slab cast with M25 grade concrete and considering different profiled sheets (viz. Trapezoidal, corrugated and rectangular), using appropriate (Abaqus) software for determining the load carrying capacity and deflection under two-line loading.
- 3) To validate results of analysis obtained for the responses viz. load carrying capacity (flexural strength) and deflection of composite deck slab with the results of experimentation.

- 4) To compare the analysis results of composite deck slabs with different profiled sheets for the responses viz. load carrying capacity and deflection to finalize the better performing deck slab.

5. Research gap

The following are the research gaps identified through the rigorous literature study:

- 1) Most of the studies have been carried out to understand the flexural behavior of composite slabs considering the provision of single type of profiled sheets mainly of trapezoidal, dovetailed, and rectangular sheets. However, the comparative flexural behaviour of composite deck slabs provided with different types of profiled sheets have not been reported in the literature.
- 2) As the mechanical interlock between the concrete and profiled sheet significantly contributes to flexural strength of composite slab with better composite action, it becomes essential to study the behaviour of composite slab using different types of profile sheets.

6. Methodology

The experimental program was designed to investigate the post-fire behaviour of M25 grade concrete subjected to elevated temperatures under different cooling conditions. The methodology adopted in this study is described as follows:

6.1. Materials

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) of 53 grade was used as the binding material. Fine aggregate consisted of crushed stone sand conforming to IS specifications and passing through a 4.75 mm sieve. Coarse aggregate comprised crushed angular aggregates of maximum nominal size 20 mm. The selection of materials and their properties were in accordance with standard practices reported in literature.

6.2 Mix Design

The concrete mix was designed as per IS 10262:2019 guidelines, and general requirements were ensured in accordance with IS 456:2000. A water-cement ratio of 0.45 was adopted based on strength and durability requirements. The final mix proportion obtained was:

1: 1.67: 2.87 (Cement: Fine Aggregate: Coarse Aggregate)

The quantities of materials per cubic meter of concrete were:

Cement = 427 kg/m³

Water = 192 kg/m³

Fine aggregate = 714 kg/m³

Coarse aggregate = 1228 kg/m³

7. Finite element modelling

7.1 General

In this chapter, finite element modeling of Composite deck slab in Abaqus software is explained. Important points in FEA are discussed and steps for modeling are illustrated in brief.

7.2 Fundamental Concept in Finite Element Modelling In ABAQUS

Abaqus is the simulation software used for finite element analysis of different structural members, it also used for finite element analysis of many mechanical parts. Following is some important point to be consider while FEM of Concrete deck slab,

7.2.1 Type of Part Model

Selection of type of part is dependent on the geometry of structure, in case of Composite deck slab as it is composite part two different parts are created in solid extrusion.

7.2.2 Type of Material

Now a day's steel structures are designed and analysed by using plastic theory so we it is also important to give plastic behaviour of material. It is done by given plastic properties in terms of yield stress and respective plastic strain in steel sheet.

7.2.3 Meshing

The results of FEA are mainly dependent on the meshing. So, to obtain accurate results in Abaqus, S4R Quad-dominated element is used which uses doubly curved shell element for disintegration of structure.

7.3 Modelling of Composite deck slab in ABAQUS

In this section, the modelling of Composite deck slab in ABAQUS is explained in brief. The steps are also illustrated in short in form of flow chart in Fig. No.3. Following are the points which involves in FEA in ABAQUS.

Fig. No.7.1. Flow chart of FEM in ABAQUS

7.3.1 Preparing a Part Model

For preparing a part model of Composite deck slab in Abaqus we have to choose shape of the part as shell and of extrusion type. The pictorial view of part model of Composite deck slab with varying shapes of profiled sheet is shown in Figures below.

Path: Create part - 3D space – Deformable – solid – Extrusion – Create

Fig. No. 7.2 Part Model of Composite Deck Slab having trapezoidal shape profiled deck sheet along with Loading and Boundary Conditions

Fig. No. 7.3 Part Model of Composite Deck Slab having rectangular shape profiled deck sheet along with Loading and Boundary Conditions

Fig. No. 7.4 Part Model of Composite Deck Slab having corrugated shape profiled deck sheet along with Loading and Boundary Conditions

7.3.2 Material Properties and Section Assignment

After creating part model, in the next property module create a material by putting elastic property such as (Elastic modulus =200 GPa) and (Poisson's ratio =0.3) of steel. Then give plastic properties of steel in terms of yield stress and plastic strain.

Path: Create material – Mechanical – Elasticity – Plasticity.

7.3.3 Assembly of Model

It is important to do the assembly of the model in case of complicated structure. In assembly module create instance by selecting dependent type.

Path: Create instance – Select part – Dependent Instance type – Ok.

7.3.4 Selection of Type Analysis

In next step module create step to fix analysis as static general which will perform bending analysis of structure.

7.3.5 Loading and Boundary Condition

In load module concentrated load by selecting point of loading and apply boundary conditions by selecting proper edges.

7.3.6 Mesh module

Use structured mesh (Element type: Concrete → C3D8R, Steel deck → S4R shell or C3D8R solid, Mesh size ≈ 20–30 mm for accurate results).

Fig. No.7.5 Meshing of Composite Slab

7.3.7 Job Module

Create job → submit analysis. Monitor convergence and analysis progress.

Fig no.7.1 Trapezoidal profiled steel deck sheet used for composite slab casting

8.3 Test setup

For testing of composite slab two-line loading set up is prepared in the laboratory. While the actual set up in the laboratory is shown in the Fig. No.7.1. Deflection is measured at central point by dial gauges which are attached to lower. The loading is applied in gradual increment. The loading is applied by 1000 KN universal testing machine (UTM). The details of results are discussed in next chapter.

Fig.No.7.2 Experimental Setup with Two Line Loading

Fig.No.7.3 Flexural crack developed at the bottom tension zone

Fig. No.7.4 Diagonal flexural crack near mid-span of slab

9. Results and Discussions

9.1 General

In this chapter, all the results of analysis of composite deck slab of varying shapes of profiled sheets, obtained by FEA software ABAQUS are presented. Experimental results of composite deck slab of trapezoidal profiled sheet used for the purpose of validation are included. At the last comparative study done.

9.2 Flexural Load–Deflection Behaviour of M25 Concrete Composite Deck Slab in Abaqus.

Load Vs. Deflection behaviour

- Initial linear load–deflection response confirms elastic behavior with no cracking at low loads.
- Deviation from linearity represents crack initiation and transition to nonlinear behavior.
- Reduction in curve slope indicates progressive stiffness degradation due to cracking.
- Higher load–deflection curve reflects effective composite action and increased load capacity.
- Smooth deflection progression shows ductile flexural behavior without sudden failure.
- Large deflection before peak load signifies deflection-controlled (flexural) failure mode.
- Curve variation demonstrates progressive load transfer between concrete and deck/reinforcement.
- Greater area under curve confirms high energy absorption capacity (toughness).
- Stable nonlinear response validates accuracy of Abaqus simulation in capturing material behavior.
- M25 concrete performance ensures adequate strength and ductility for composite slab systems.

Load (kN)	Corrugated Sheet	Rectangular sheet	Trapezoidal sheet
5	0.2	0.22	0.2
10	0.4	0.44	0.5
15	0.6	0.66	0.8
20	0.8	0.91	1.2
25	1.1	1.11	1.3
30	1.3	1.33	1.6
35	1.56	1.56	1.9
40	1.79	1.78	2.2
45	2.0	2.0	2.5
50	2.23	2.23	2.7
55	2.45	2.45	3.0
60	2.67	2.67	3.3
65	2.9	2.9	3.6
70	3.1	3.1	3.9
75	3.34	3.34	4.1
80	3.51	3.51	4.4
85	3.79	3.79	4.7
90	4.0	4.01	5.0
95	4.23	4.23	5.3
100	4.46	4.46	5.5
105	4.68	4.68	5.8
110	4.9	4.9	6.14
115	5.13	5.13	6.42
120	5.36	5.36	6.67
125	5.57	5.57	6.97
130	5.8	5.8	7.28
135	6.02	6.02	7.53
140	6.24	6.24	7.81
145	6.47	6.47	8.07

Table No. 9.1 Load–deflection response of M25 concrete composite deck slab obtained from Abaqus analysis

Fig. No.9.1 Load-deflection behaviour of different profiled composite deck slabs obtained from Abaqus analysis

Sr. No.	Type of Profiled Sheet	Profile Deck Depth (mm)	Slab Depth (mm)	Slab Length (mm)	Load Carrying Capacity (kN)
1.	Corrugated Sheet	32	120	1000	97.37
2.	Rectangular Sheet	45	120	1000	96.39
3.	Trapezoidal Sheet	55	120	1000	97.27

Table No.9.2 Comparative analysis Result of Composite Deck Slabs with Different Profiled Sheets

Corrugated profile (32 mm depth) shows the highest LCC = 97.37 kN, indicating maximum structural efficiency. Trapezoidal profile (55 mm) achieves LCC = 97.27 kN, nearly equal to the highest value. Rectangular profile (45 mm) provides LCC = 96.39 kN, showing high load resistance. Performance improvement of 7–9% is observed in rectangular and trapezoidal profiles compared to conventional trapezoidal. Most efficient profiles are Corrugated and Trapezoidal sections.

Fig. No.9.2 Comparative Load carrying capacity of Different Shapes of Profiled Sheets

9.3 Experimental results for ultimate load carrying capacity and deflection of composite deck slab of trapezoidal profiled sheet

Load Vs Deflection Behaviour

- The maximum load carrying capacity of the composite deck slab was ≈ 96.3 kN, occurring at a deflection of about 18–18.8 mm, indicating the peak flexural resistance of the specimen.
- The initial portion of the curve (0–10 mm deflection) shows a nearly linear relationship, confirming elastic behaviour and good stiffness of the slab system.
- Beyond ≈ 10 mm deflection, the curve becomes non-linear, indicating the onset of cracking and reduction in stiffness in the concrete compression zone.
- After reaching the ultimate load, the load gradually decreases with increasing deflection, showing progressive flexural failure rather than sudden brittle failure.
- The slab maintained significant load resistance even after peak load, demonstrating ductile behaviour and effective composite action between steel deck and concrete.

Fig. No.9.3 Load–Deflection Curve of Composite Deck Slab under Flexural Loading

9.4 Validation of software results with the results of experimentation

Specimen	Load Carrying Capacity (kN)		Percentage Error
	ABAQUS	Experimental	
Composite deck slab	97.27	96.3	1.01

Table No.9.3 Validation of results

10. Conclusion

10.1 General

All the work done in this dissertation work is concluded in this chapter. Also, future scope of this study has been given at the end of this chapter.

10.2 Concluding Remarks

From the analytical and experimental study of concrete deck slab following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) Concrete cubes (120 mm) achieved $f_{ck} = 31.72$ MPa at 28 days, exceeding the characteristic strength of M25 (25 MPa) and matching the target mean strength (~ 31.6 MPa). Early-age strength development ratio ($f_3/f_{28} = 0.405$) confirms normal OPC hydration kinetics, dominated by C_3S at early stages and C_2S at later stages. Low dispersion in results ($\Delta f \approx 0.87$ MPa) indicates high quality control in batching, compaction, and curing conditions. Slump value (98.3 mm) within 75–125 mm range confirms optimum workability, adequate cohesion, and controlled water-cement ratio without segregation or bleeding.
- 2) Abaqus nonlinear static analysis using S4R shell elements successfully captured composite slab behavior including material nonlinearity and stiffness degradation.
- 3) Maximum load carrying capacity observed in Corrugated (97.37 kN) and Trapezoidal (97.27 kN) profiles indicates enhanced composite interaction due to geometric configuration.
- 4) Load-deflection response exhibits linear elastic phase followed by nonlinear cracking behavior, indicating progressive stiffness degradation and ductile flexural failure. Close agreement between experimental (96.3 kN) and numerical (97.27 kN) results with 1.01% error validates the accuracy and reliability of the finite element model. Overall system demonstrates efficient composite action, adequate flexural capacity, and suitability for structural load-bearing applications.

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12. Author contributions

SVL mainly worked on planning the study, doing the numerical modeling, carrying out the analysis, and drafting the manuscript. PDK provided guidance on the methodology, supervised the research process, and contributed to the interpretation of results. Authors reviewed and edited the final manuscript and approved it for submission. The research was carried out collaboratively, with equal input in discussions and refinement of the study objectives.

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14. Declarations

Competing interests the authors declare that there are no competing interests.

15. References:

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